

A review of 2050 Calculators and their academic and policy influence

Author(s): F. Kiley*

*Corresponding author, Imperial College London

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Abstract

This review provides a comprehensive assessment of the 2050 Calculator programme, examining its global development, structural characteristics, and academic and policy influence. Originating in the United Kingdom in 2010, the calculator framework has expanded to 128 unique models tailored to national, regional, and city contexts. The analysis reveals that while the majority of calculators focus on high- and upper-middle-income countries, there remains a significant gap in representation for low-income nations. Calculator complexity varies widely, enabling use across a spectrum of audiences, from the general public to technical experts. However, challenges remain regarding long-term accessibility and the transparency of input data and assumptions, limiting academic engagement and model scrutiny.

The review identifies 54 peer-reviewed academic papers and 24 policy documents that incorporate or are informed by the calculators. These span a diverse set of themes including renewable energy, energy security, employment, food systems, and decarbonisation pathways. Notably, the calculators have directly contributed to long-term strategy development in countries such as the UK, India, Nigeria, and Austria. Overall, the findings highlight the versatility and policy relevance of the calculator framework. To maximise future impact, ongoing support, improved data transparency, and broader global coverage will be essential for advancing inclusive and evidence-based climate action.

1.0 Introduction

Addressing the global challenge of climate change requires a fundamental transformation across all sectors of the economy to achieve net zero greenhouse gas emissions. In recent years, governments around the world have set increasingly ambitious targets in response to this need. Among them, the United Kingdom has enshrined in law a commitment to reach net zero emissions by 2050, while the Paris Agreement, a legally binding international treaty, aims to limit global temperature rise to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels.

Achieving such goals relies on evidence-based policymaking grounded in robust, quantitative energy and emissions modelling. A wide array of modelling tools exist, ranging from bottom-up simulations to econometric and optimisation frameworks, each offering unique strengths and limitations. These models can appear opaque, particularly to non-expert policymakers and the general public. Furthermore, due to uncertainties around future technologies, consumer behaviour, and the broad impact of net zero, there is a growing demand for accessible, transparent, and engaging tools to support public dialogue and policy development.

In response to this need, the UK government launched the 2050 Calculator in 2010. This tool was developed through a participatory process involving a broad range of stakeholders who helped define its boundaries and sector-specific levers. It was designed to be usable by the public, policymakers, and technical experts alike, allowing users to explore the impact of different policy and technology choices on the country's emissions trajectory. The calculator supported the UK's strategy to reduce emissions by 80% from 1990 levels by 2050, a target later increased to 100%. It informed the UK's 2011 emissions reduction strategy and has since seen widespread public engagement.

Following its success, the UK Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC) initiated an international programme to support other countries in developing their own national calculators. In 2012, the UK's International Climate Fund provided resources to assist ten developing countries in adapting the tool to their specific national contexts. These calculators remain open-source, transparent, and interactive by design. Technically, they follow a bottom-up simulation approach, with inputs derived through stakeholder engagement and peer review. They simulate physically and technically plausible energy futures up to 2050 by allowing users to adjust levers, representing varying levels of ambition, for different technologies, behaviours, and infrastructure decisions. These levers shape "pathways," with results displayed in real time, providing immediate feedback on their implications.

Despite their broad application and policy relevance, there has been no comprehensive academic review of the development and impact of these calculators. Existing literature has been limited in scope, focusing primarily on their role in education rather than their wider influence on policy or scholarship. This paper aims to address that gap by conducting a comprehensive assessment of all calculators developed under the DECC/DESNZ programme, as well as others based on the same foundational structure. It further presents a literature review of peer-reviewed publications and policy documents that have used these calculators, in order to assess their academic and policy contributions to date.

1.1 Overview of the UK 2050 Calculators

Three main versions of the calculator were developed: My2050, a gamified tool for public engagement (Figure 1), a web-based version aimed at a broader audience with a simplified interface (Figure 2), and the full model, built in Excel with transparent calculations and customisable assumptions (Figure 3).

Figure 1: Screenshot of the MacKay version of My2050

Figure 2: Screenshot of the MacKay version of the web tool

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Manual Level Selection and Model Level Values Applied	Manual Level Selection	Description of Levers	Example Pathways									
Manual Choices	Manual Level	Manual End	Manual Start	Manual End	Manual Start	Manual End	Manual Start	Manual End	Manual Start	Manual End	Manual Start	Manual End
AmbDemUnit.d0P Domestic passenger travel demand	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.Walk Walking share of passenger travel demand	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.Cycl Cycling share of passenger travel demand	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.carAL Car share of passenger travel demand	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.busAL Bus share of passenger travel demand	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.trnPA Rail share of passenger travel demand	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.avD Aviation share of passenger travel demand	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.intl International passenger travel demand	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.carALL Car Occupancy/sharing rates	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.carALL Car own or hire (average vehicle mileage)	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.carE Car - Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.carH Car - Hydrogen vehicle distance share	1	2020	25	1	2020	25	1	2020	25	1	2020	25
AmbDemUnit.carPH Car - Plug-in Hybrid Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.lgE LGV - Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.lgH LGV - Hydrogen vehicle distance share	1	2020	25	1	2020	25	1	2020	25	1	2020	25
AmbDemUnit.lgPH LGV - Plug-in Hybrid Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.hgE Rigid - Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.hgH Rigid - Hydrogen vehicle distance share	1	2020	25	1	2020	25	1	2020	25	1	2020	25
AmbDemUnit.hgPH Rigid - Plug-in Hybrid Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.hgE Articulated - Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.hgH Articulated - Hydrogen vehicle distance share	1	2020	25	1	2020	25	1	2020	25	1	2020	25
AmbDemUnit.hgPH Articulated - Plug-in Hybrid Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.busE Bus - Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.busH Bus - Hydrogen vehicle distance share	1	2020	25	1	2020	25	1	2020	25	1	2020	25
AmbDemUnit.busPH Bus - Plug-in Hybrid Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.trnPE Rail Passenger - Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.trnFE Rail Freight - Electric vehicle distance share	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.carAL Car - Biofuel share of liquid fuel	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.lgAL LGV - Biofuel share of liquid fuel	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.hgR Rigid - Biofuel share of liquid fuel	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.hgA Articulated - Biofuel share of liquid fuel	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.busAL Bus - Biofuel share of liquid fuel	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.trnPA Rail Passenger - Biofuel share of liquid fuel	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.trnFA Rail Freight - Biofuel share of liquid fuel	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.nrm Non Road Mobile Machinery - Biofuel share of liquid fuel	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30
AmbDemUnit.dem chb Domestic Domestic - Biofuel share of liquid fuel	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30	1	2020	30

Figure 3: Screenshot of the MacKay full excel model

The calculator received praise in a government quality assurance review for its transparency and usability, attracting 150,000 unique users by 2013 and delivering diplomatic benefits through international interest and uptake. For example, the development of the China 2050 Pathways Calculator in 2012 with support from DECC demonstrated easing of Anglo-Chinese relations. Since 2012,

The calculators employ a system of levers that span all major sectors of the economy, enabling users to model a wide range of decarbonisation strategies. In the original full Excel version of the UK calculator, 43 levers were included, covering sectors such as electricity generation, bioenergy supply, transport, households, business, geosequestration, balancing and storage, and domestic fossil fuel production. The updated MacKay calculator significantly expanded this structure to include 162 levers, maintaining a similar sectoral breakdown while allowing for more detailed and nuanced scenario development.

Each lever is defined according to four levels of “effort,” which represent progressively more ambitious actions: Level 1 reflects minimal or no change; Level 2 indicates ambitious yet reasonable measures; Level 3 requires very ambitious action, potentially involving technical breakthroughs; and Level 4 represents the upper bound of what is considered technically plausible. This structure allows users to systematically explore the implications of different levels of ambition across the entire economy.

2.0 Methodology

Calculators were identified primarily through three main websites that list and host national and regional 2050 calculator tools: the Imperial College London 2050 Calculator site, the 2050 Calculator Network, and the Pathways Explorer community platform. Using these sources, along with broader searches of academic and grey literature, a comprehensive database was compiled of all publicly available and documented calculators.

This database captured a range of key characteristics for each calculator, including its name, year of publication, source, geographic scope, country focus, sectoral coverage, number of levers, availability of the calculator and its data, ownership, and the versions available. Collecting this information enabled a structured analysis of the calculators' architecture, publication trends, geographic and socio-economic applicability, complexity, transparency, and inclusivity.

To assess the academic and political impact of the calculators, two main approaches were used. For academic impact, searches were conducted in SCOPUS and ScienceDirect using targeted keywords to identify peer-reviewed publications that referenced or used the calculators. For political impact, grey literature and government policy documents were identified through systematic Google searches. While this approach does not guarantee comprehensive coverage, it provides useful insight into the influence and practical application of these tools in policy contexts.

Figure 4 details the workflow executed in this literature review; Table AX contains a comprehensive account of search terms used, results returned, and results retained of the review of academic literature.

Figure 4: Flowchart detailing process employed to identify and analyse calculators and related publications

3.0 Results

A comprehensive database of key details of all the calculators can be found in the Supplementary Information file accompanying this paper.

3.1 Geographic Scope and Scale of Calculators

Across the databases outlined in the Methods section, a total of 128 individual calculators were identified across 55 different countries. Several countries had more than one calculator associated with them; Belgium, for example, had the highest number with ten calculators, four of which are provincial and two cover specific cities. When multiple calculators covered the same geographic area, they were treated as distinct entries if they differed significantly in structure or date of publication. For instance, two calculators focus on the European Union (EU): EUCalc and CLIMACT's 2050 Pathways Explorer EU27. Despite their shared scope, they are structurally different – EUCalc includes 59 levers, including those related to biodiversity, while EU27 offers 227 levers with no explicit biodiversity component. Notably, both calculators also allow users to focus on individual EU member states, enabling country-specific lever selection and visualisation. As a result, each of these EU-wide calculators effectively contributes an additional 28 national-level calculators to the overall count. Table A1 provides a comprehensive list of countries and regions with their associated calculators, along with the number of calculators linked to each.

Figure 5: Map illustrating the list of countries along with the number of calculators linked to each

The original UK calculator was developed at the national level; however, the creation process was intentionally designed to be flexible and adaptable to the unique characteristics of different geographic contexts. As shown in **Figure 6**, while most calculators have been developed at the national scale, nearly 25% were created for city, provincial, regional, or even global applications. This demonstrates the versatility of the calculator framework and its utility in generating valuable insights across a range of spatial scales.

Figure 6: The geographic range of the developed calculators with the associated frequency

3.2 Socio-Economic Range and Emissions

The geographic coverage of the calculators covers a range of countries of different socio-economic status, from the lower-middle income Nigeria to the high-income United States of America. **Figure 7** shows the proportion of each income classification represented by the calculators. There is a clear skew towards more developed economies, with 91% of calculators covering countries classified as either Upper-Middle or High income. To date, no Low-income countries are represented. This could reflect the relative importance of decarbonising more developed economies due to their greater total and annual emissions. However, this disparity points to a significant gap in access to decision-support tools in regions that may be disproportionately vulnerable to the impacts of climate change and face unique development challenges. Addressing this imbalance will be crucial to ensuring inclusive and globally coordinated climate action.

Figure 7: The proportion of calculators covering the income classification as assigned by the World Bank's 2026 update.

As seen in **Figure 8**, the calculators cover 73% of global emissions as of 2024, including major emitters such as China (15,536 Mt CO₂eq/yr), the United States (5,913 Mt CO₂eq/yr), and India (4,371 Mt CO₂eq/yr). This broad coverage highlights the strategic relevance of these tools in supporting emissions reduction planning across the world's highest-emitting economies.

Figure 8: The quantity of emissions covered by countries with associated calculators compared to countries with no calculators, in Mt CO₂eq/yr

3.3 Timeline of Publication

Figure 9 presents a timeline of calculator releases, beginning with the original UK 2050 Calculator launched in 2010. The 29 calculators released between 2012 and 2016 align with the UK Department of Energy and Climate Change's (DECC) initial international outreach programme,

supported by UK International Climate Finance. A notable peak in 2019 corresponds to the launch of EUCalc by CLIMACT, which alone accounted for 29 individual calculators – one for the EU as a whole and 28 for each member state (including the UK). This trend continued in 2025 with the release of CLIMACT’s 2050 Pathways Explorers, again covering all 28 European countries, in addition to three provincial calculators and 19 city-level versions. The sustained development and regular updates of calculators over more than a decade highlight their continued relevance as both public engagement tools and practical instruments for informing policy. Their endurance is further evidenced by ongoing political support, including consistent backing from successive UK governments, reflecting the model's cross-party appeal and institutional value.

Figure 9: A timeline of when the calculators were released

3.4 Complexity and Sectoral Coverage

The number of levers included in each calculator serves as a useful proxy for assessing its complexity, with a higher number of levers allowing for more detailed modelling of sectoral decisions and interactions within the energy system. Among the calculators reviewed, lever counts range from 33 in the simplest tools to 227 in the most complex, demonstrating the framework’s adaptability to varying levels of user expertise and analytical needs. For example, the online version of the MacKay Calculator contains 45 levers, striking a balance between accessibility and depth, while the full Excel version includes 162 levers and is designed for expert users engaged in evidence-based policymaking. **Figure 10** shows the number of calculators with the corresponding number of levers.

Three distinct peaks in lever counts, at 59, 218, and 227, correspond to EUCalc, various city-level calculators, and CLIMACT’s 2050 Pathways Explorer, respectively. The latter includes tools developed not only for EU member states but also for countries such as China, India, the United States, and Georgia, as well as several provincial-level calculators in Belgium. This trend toward

greater complexity, particularly in CLIMACT-developed tools, reflects a growing demand for more granular, customisable models that can support detailed and context-specific policy analysis.

It should be noted that lever data could not be identified for 24 calculators due to limited availability or documentation. In many cases, only simplified online versions of the calculators remain accessible or supported, which may skew the overall dataset toward lower levels of complexity. Despite these limitations, the range and distribution of lever counts provide valuable insight into how the calculators have been tailored to different use cases and audiences.

Figure 10: The number of levers associated with each calculator

Analysis of sectoral coverage across the calculators reveals a consistent focus on core areas such as industry and manufacturing, buildings, transport, and energy or electricity supply, as shown in [Figure 11](#). These sectors are included in the majority of calculators, reflecting their significant contribution to national emissions and their centrality in most decarbonisation strategies. In contrast, sectors such as diet, carbon dioxide removal, waste, and biodiversity are included far less frequently. This disparity suggests that while calculators are well equipped to model traditional high-emitting sectors, they may underrepresent emerging or cross-cutting areas that are increasingly recognised as important to achieving comprehensive net-zero outcomes. The limited inclusion of these sectors may be due to challenges in data availability, modelling complexity, or differing national priorities. Expanding coverage to include these underrepresented areas could enhance the ability of calculators to support more integrated and holistic climate policy development.

Figure 11: Sectoral coverage of the calculators.

3.5 Calculator and Data Availability

The limited availability of calculators and their underlying data poses significant challenges for academic and research use. When web tools are no longer supported or accessible, researchers are unable to interact with the models, replicate pathways, or conduct comparative analyses, which restricts their utility for academia. Although 79% of calculators remain available in some form, typically via simplified web interfaces, the removal of support for many tools illustrates the fragility of their digital footprint and the risk of obsolescence over time.

Furthermore, only 52 percent of calculators provide access to their input data and modelling assumptions in a clear and usable format. This lack of transparency undermines one of the core principles of the calculator framework: openness and clarity in how results are generated. Without access to these inputs, users are unable to scrutinize the methodological foundations of the models, assess the validity of assumptions, and evaluate the quality of the scenarios produced. This creates a barrier not only for academics conducting research but also for policymakers and stakeholders seeking to make informed decisions based on reliable evidence. Improving long-term accessibility and data transparency is therefore essential to support both academic engagement and the broader credibility of the calculator framework.

Figures 12(a) and (b) illustrate calculator and data availability respectively.

Figure 12: Availability of calculators (a) and input data and assumptions (b)

3.6 Academic and Policy Impact

In addition to examining the structure, geographic scope, transparency, and customisability of the 2050 calculators, this study also assesses their academic and policy impact. **Figure 13** highlights the number of policy papers and academic papers that have been written using the calculators. A total of 54 peer-reviewed academic publications were identified across various calculators, demonstrating their growing relevance as research tools. India accounts for the highest number of academic studies (18), with papers exploring themes such as the feasibility of 100% renewable energy supply, energy security, net-zero implications for employment, sustainable development, air quality, energy storage, and the compatibility of economic growth with deep decarbonisation. These studies highlight the calculator’s ability to support scenario analysis at the intersection of climate, energy, and socio-economic planning.

The Global Calculator has similarly informed academic research, with nine papers covering wide-ranging themes including global mitigation pathways, the co-benefits of climate policy for public

health, food security, power system adequacy, and the physical and economic constraints of bioenergy. These analyses demonstrate the tool's versatility in addressing cross-sectoral and systems-level challenges at the global scale. EUCalc has been used in seven academic studies focused on the role of lifestyle change in decarbonisation, land-use dynamics, heavy-duty transport, and sector-specific transitions in buildings and agriculture. The presence of four academic papers on the Taiwan calculator, focused on net-zero power systems, energy efficiency, and food waste, further illustrates the calculator's applicability in diverse regional contexts.

Beyond academia, 24 policy papers have been published using the calculators in their methodology with several calculators directly informing national and subnational climate and energy policies. Notable examples include the UK's Carbon Plan, Austria's Long-Term Strategy 2050, the Czech Republic's Climate Protection Policy, India's Draft National Energy Policy, Nigeria's Renewable Energy Roadmap developed with IRENA, and the Philippines' Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC). These cases demonstrate the calculator's value not only as an analytical and engagement tool but also as an instrument that bridges modelling and policymaking. The range of themes explored in the academic literature, from technology adoption and air quality to food systems and employment, underscores the calculator's role in enabling integrated, long-term strategy development. This combined academic and policy impact affirms the continued relevance of the 2050 calculator framework as a flexible and transparent tool for navigating complex climate and energy transitions.

Despite the substantial number of academic and policy publications related to the 2050 calculators, only 14 of the 55 countries with associated calculators have at least one academic or policy paper linked to their use. This disparity highlights a significant gap between tool development and documented impact, suggesting that while calculators are being created across a wide geographic range, their integration into formal academic discourse or national policy processes remains limited in most contexts. This finding raises important questions about the capacity, institutional support, and visibility required to translate tool availability into meaningful influence. It also points to the need for more systematic efforts to support uptake, application, and evaluation of the calculators in underrepresented regions to ensure that the potential of these tools is fully realised.

It must be noted that this analysis does not constitute a comprehensive record of all academic and policy papers that have been informed by the calculators but serves to act as an indication as to their utility in such contexts.

Figure 13: Number of policy briefs, reports, and strategies and number of academic publications that utilise the calculators in their methodologies

4.0 Conclusion

This review demonstrates the enduring relevance and versatility of the 2050 Calculator framework as a tool for modelling national and subnational decarbonisation pathways. Since its inception in the UK in 2010, the framework has evolved into a global initiative encompassing 128 calculators across 55 countries. These tools have been adapted to diverse geographic and socio-economic contexts, from global and regional scales to individual cities, reflecting their flexible design and broad applicability. Despite the initial concentration of development in high-income countries – 91% of calculators were created for upper-middle and high-income nations – the absence of tools tailored to low-income countries points to a critical gap in global modelling equity. Addressing this will be essential for inclusive climate planning.

The structural diversity of the calculators, particularly in the number of levers used, illustrates their adaptability to varying levels of complexity and audience needs. However, this review also identifies significant limitations. Many calculators are no longer accessible or maintained, and only about half offer transparent access to input data and modelling assumptions. This restricts both academic utility and public accountability.

Nonetheless, the influence of the calculators is evident. Over 50 academic papers have employed them to explore issues including renewable energy, energy security, employment, air quality, and land use. In parallel, 24 policy strategies and plans have incorporated them into national and subnational climate action, including in India, Austria, Nigeria, and the UK. Yet this influence remains uneven: only 14 of the 55 countries with calculators have documented academic or policy outputs linked to their use, highlighting the need for stronger institutional support, visibility, and integration.

To ensure the continued impact of the calculator framework, sustained maintenance, improved transparency, and targeted expansion to underserved regions will be vital. As a publicly accessible, adaptable, and policy-relevant tool, the 2050 Calculator remains uniquely positioned to support the design of robust, inclusive, and science-based climate strategies.

Annex

A1 Search terms used in SCOPUS and Science Direct

Country	Database	Search Terms	Results Returned	Results Retained	Citation Chasing
European Union	SCOPUS	"2050 Pathways Explorer" "EUCalc"	9	3	0
	Science Direct	"2050 Pathways Explorer" "EUCalc"	15	4	2
Global	SCOPUS	"Global Calculator"	8	2	0
	Science Direct	"Global Calculator"	19	6	1
Southeast Europe	SCOPUS	"SEE 2050 Calculator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"SEE 2050 Calculator"	0	0	0
Australia	SCOPUS	Australia 2050 Pathways Calculator	0	0	0
	Science Direct	Australia 2050 Pathways Calculator	0	0	0
Austria	SCOPUS	2050 Pathways for Austria	0	0	0
	Science Direct	2050 Pathways for Austria	0	0	0
Bangladesh	SCOPUS	Bangladesh 2050 Energy and Emissions Calculator OR "BD2050"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	Bangladesh 2050 Energy and Emissions Calculator OR "BD2050"	1	1	1
Belgium	SCOPUS	Belgian 2050 Pathways Calculator OR "Belgium 2050 Pathways Calculator" OR "2050 Pathways Explorer" OR (Wallonia AND Calculator)	2	0	0
	Science Direct	Belgian 2050 Pathways Calculator OR "Belgium 2050 Pathways Calculator" OR "2050 Pathways Explorer" OR (Wallonia AND "2050 Calculator")	3	1	0

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Brazil	SCOPUS	"Brazil Energy Policy Simulator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"Brazil Energy Policy Simulator"	0	0	0
Bulgaria*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
China	SCOPUS	"China 2050 Pathways Calculator" OR "China 2050 Pathways Energy Calculator" OR "China 2050 Calculator"	1	0	0
	Science Direct	"China 2050 Pathways Calculator" OR "China 2050 Pathways Energy Calculator" OR "China 2050 Calculator"	5	2	0
Colombia	SCOPUS	Colombia 2050 Carbon Calculator	0	0	0
	Science Direct	Colombia 2050 Carbon Calculator	0	0	0
Croatia*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Cyprus*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Czech Republic*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Denmark*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Ecuador	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Estonia*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Finland*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
France*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Georgia*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Germany*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				

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Greece*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Hungary*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
India	SCOPUS	"India Energy Security Scenarios"	5	3	0
	Science Direct	"India Energy Security Scenarios"	36	14	1
Indonesia	SCOPUS	"Indonesia Net Zero Emission Calculator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"Indonesia Net Zero Emission Calculator"	0	0	0
Italy*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Japan	SCOPUS	"Japan 2050 Low Carbon Navigator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"Japan 2050 Low Carbon Navigator"	4	2	0
Kenya	SCOPUS	KCERT 2050 OR "KCERT2050"	1	1	0
	Science Direct	KCERT 2050 OR "KCERT2050"	0	0	0
Latvia*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Lithuania*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Luxembourg*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Malaysia	SCOPUS	"Malaysia Climate Action Simulator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"Malaysia Climate Action Simulator"	0	0	0
Malta*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Mauritius	SCOPUS	"Mauritius 2050 Pathways Calculator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"Mauritius 2050 Pathways Calculator"	0	0	0
Mexico	SCOPUS	"Mexico 2050 Calculator"	1	1	0
	Science Direct	"Mexico 2050 Calculator"	0	0	0
Netherlands*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
New Zealand	SCOPUS	"Wellington 2050 Energy Calculator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"Wellington 2050 Energy Calculator"	0	0	0

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Nigeria	SCOPUS	"NECAL 2050" OR "NECAL2050" OR "NECAL2060" OR "NECAL 2060"	3	3	1
	Science Direct	"NECAL 2050" OR "NECAL2050" OR "NECAL2060" OR "NECAL 2060"	7	0	0
Poland*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Portugal*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Philippines	SCOPUS	"Philippine Emissions Pathways Calculator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"Philippine Emissions Pathways Calculator"	0	0	0
Republic of Ireland	SCOPUS	"Ireland 2050"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"Ireland 2050"	14	0	0
Romania*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Slovakia*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Slovenia*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
South Africa	SCOPUS	"South Africa 2050 Calculator" OR "2050 Pathways Calculator for South Africa"	1	0	0
	Science Direct	"South Africa 2050 Calculator" OR "2050 Pathways Calculator for South Africa"	0	0	0
South Korea	SCOPUS	"South Korea" AND "2050 Greenhouse Gas Emission Pathways Calculator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"South Korea" AND "2050 Greenhouse Gas Emission Pathways Calculator"	0	0	0
Spain*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Sweden*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				
Switzerland*	SCOPUS				
	Science Direct				

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Taiwan	SCOPUS	"taiwan 2050 calculator"	4	3	0
	Science Direct	"taiwan 2050 calculator"	9	2	0
Thailand	SCOPUS	"Thailand 2050 Pathways Calculator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"Thailand 2050 Pathways Calculator"	0	0	0
United States	SCOPUS	"US Energy Calculator"	0	0	0
	Science Direct	"US Energy Calculator"	0	0	0
United Kingdom	SCOPUS	"MacKay Carbon Calculator"	5	1	0
		"UK Pathways Calculator"			
	Science Direct	"MacKay Carbon Calculator" "UK Pathways Calculator"	0	0	0
Vietnam	SCOPUS		0	0	0
	Science Direct	"Vietnam2050calculator4ndc"	0	0	0

* Calculators are included in EUCalc or 2050 Pathways Explorer so do not require additional searches

A2 Full list of countries with calculators

Table A1: Full list of countries and regions with associated calculators

Country/Region	Number of Calculators	Income Status in 2024
European Union	2	High
Global	1	n/a
Southeast Europe	1	High
Australia	1	High
Austria	3	High
Bangladesh	1	Lower-Middle
Belgium	10	High
Brazil	2	High
Bulgaria	2	Upper-Middle
China	4	Upper-Middle
Colombia	1	Upper-Middle
Croatia	5	High
Cyprus	2	High
Czech Republic	4	High
Denmark	2	High
Ecuador	1	Upper-Middle
Estonia	2	High
Finland	2	High
France	5	High
Georgia	1	Upper-Middle
Germany	2	High
Greece	2	High
Hungary	3	High
India	4	Lower-Middle
Indonesia	4	Upper-Middle
Italy	3	High
Japan	2	High
Kenya	1	Lower-Middle
Latvia	4	High
Lithuania	2	High
Luxembourg	2	High
Malaysia	1	Upper-Middle
Malta	2	High
Mauritius	1	Upper-Middle
Mexico	1	Upper-Middle
Netherlands	2	High
New Zealand	1	High
Nigeria	2	Lower-Middle
Philippines	1	Lower-Middle
Poland	2	High
Portugal	6	High
Republic of Ireland	5	High

Romania	2	High
Slovakia	2	High
Slovenia	2	High
South Africa	1	Upper-Middle
South Korea	1	High
Spain	2	High
Sweden	2	High
Switzerland	2	High
Taiwan	1	High
Thailand	1	Upper-Middle
United Kingdom	3	High
United States	2	High
Vietnam	2	Lower-Middle

A3 List of Policy Papers and Academic Publications

Country/Region	Academic Papers	Policy Papers/Policies
European Union	Costa (2020) Clora & Yu (2022) Clora et al. (2021) Strapasson, Woods, Meessen, et al. (2020) Parviziomran & Bergqvist (2025) Zimmermann (2022) Wiest et al. (2022) Wiese et al. (2024)	Strapasson, Mwabonje, et al. (2020) Yu & Clora (2020) Costa (2020) Stettler et al. (2020) Gyalai-Korpos (2020) Warmuth et al. (2020) Martin & Pestiaux (2020) Baudry et al. (2020) Vitali et al. (2020)
Global	Strapasson, Woods, Pérez-Cirera, et al. (2020) Strapasson et al. (2017) Kuhnhen et al. (2020) Bailera & Lisbona (2018) Bailera et al. (2017) Abadie & Chamorro (2019) Bahar et al. (2020) Vineis et al. (2024) Garcia et al. (2022)	DECC et al. (2015)
Southeast Europe	0	0
Australia	0	0
Austria	0	BMNT (2019)
Bangladesh	Debnath & Mourshed (2024) Debnath et al. (2015)	
Belgium	0	0
Brazil	0	0
Bulgaria	0	0
China	Amakpah et al. (2016) Mischke & Karlsson (2014)	Yufeng (2018)
Colombia	0	0

Croatia	0	0
Cyprus	0	0
Czech Republic	0	MZP (2017)
Denmark	0	0
Ecuador	0	0
Estonia	0	0
Finland	0	0
France	0	0
Georgia	0	0
Germany	0	0
Greece	0	0
Hungary	0	0
India	Heredia-Fonseca et al. (2024) Kumar (2023) Chaudhuri et al. (2025) Byravan et al. (2017) Vedachalam & Atmanand (2018) B & P (2018) Dharmala et al. (2022) Kumar Shukla & Sharma (2017) Vedachalam (2018) Paladugula et al. (2018) Parikh et al. (2018) Purohit et al. (2019) Saraswat & Digalwar (2021) Singh & Rao (2016) Vedachalam et al. (2017) Xiao et al. (2021) Chabhadiya et al. (2021) Negi & Kumar (2018)	NITI Aayog (2023) NITI Aayog (2017) NITI Aayog (2015)
Indonesia	0	0
Italy	0	0
Japan	Matsumoto & Shiraki (2018) Moinuddin & Kuriyama (2019)	0
Kenya	Gachanja et al. (2023)	0
Latvia	0	0
Lithuania	0	0
Luxembourg	0	0
Malaysia	0	0
Malta	0	0
Mauritius	0	0
Mexico	Elizondo et al. (2017)	0
Netherlands	0	0
New Zealand	0	0
Nigeria	Dioha et al. (2019) Khaleel & Chakrabarti (2019) Bello & Orosun (2025) Sani Sambo et al. (2025)	IRENA (2023)

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Philippines	0	ASEAN-UK GTF (2025)
Poland	0	0
Portugal	0	0
Republic of Ireland	0	0
Romania	0	0
Slovakia	0	0
Slovenia	0	0
South Africa	0	0
South Korea	0	0
Spain	0	0
Sweden	0	0
Switzerland	0	0
Taiwan	Binyet & Hsu (2024) Budiman & Hsu (2025) Chiu et al. (2020) Tseng & Chiueh (2015) Wu et al. (2019)	0
Thailand	0	0
United Kingdom	Carvajal et al. (2022)	HM Government (2011)
United States	0	0
Vietnam	0	0